

The Factors Affecting Personal Financial Management Skills of Young Vietnamese People

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Abstract

The article examines factors affecting the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people. Based on surveys of young people in Vietnam, the research team used both qualitative and quantitative research methods to collect 161 ballots. Of these, 152 were valid ballots from young Vietnamese people and were used in the SMARTPLS software analysis of factors that affected the outcome. The results of the study showed the factors affecting the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people, including 3 factors: (1) “Awareness of personal financial management” (APFM) has the strongest influence on personal financial management skills with an influence level of 0.350; (2) “The influence of living and learning environment” (ILLE) has an impact level of 0.266; (3) “The influence of family environment” (IFE) with impact level 0.195. Thereby, the research team proposed several solutions to improve the personal financial management skills of Vietnamese youth in 3 aspects: The youth themselves; The influence of the living and learning environment (from the School), and the Family environment.

Keywords: *Influencing factors, skills, financial management, personal finance, young people, Vietnam*

1. Introduction

Financial management skills are important in personal life and business in general. Good financial management helps each person understand and adjust aspects related to money, including income and expenses, investments, savings, debt, and financial planning. (pace.edu.vn, 2024)

Young people, especially those without family ties or children, are often less constrained by financial responsibility and thus tend to easily fall into a state of uncontrolled spending. Lack of consideration in spending can easily cause young people to make financial mistakes and put themselves in difficult situations. When allocating a spending budget, we need to outline categories with fixed amounts for each purpose. More importantly, make sure to only use the fixed budget for each expense. There are many cases when we love an item but our fixed budget has been used up, we can immediately think of our current savings and “temporarily forget” our current goal. (prudential.com.vn, n.d)

This study will examine the factors affecting the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people, thereby providing some discussions on how young people can improve their financial management skills.

2. Theoretical Basis, Model, and Research Hypothesis

2.1. Basic concepts

Personal Finance

Personal finance is a term that includes managing your money as well as saving and investing. It covers budgeting, banking, insurance, mortgages, investing and retirement, taxes and estate planning. (Kenton, 2022)

Personal finance, simply understood, is the total assets of an individual or a household (including total budgets, insurance, savings books, etc.). (Dang Thuy Linh, et al, 2021)

Personal financial management

Personal financial management is financial management that includes budgeting, saving, investing, debt management, and other aspects related to personal money to achieve personal goals (Bimal Bhatt, 2011). In other words, personal financial management is the process of controlling income and organizing expenses through detailed financial planning. Learn to track income and adjust your spending to match your expenses systematically and use income.

Personal financial management is the practice of managing money, planning to spend, and saving... The purpose of personal financial management is not only to ensure that money is used effectively and avoid waste, but also to help money generate profits. In the process of personal financial management, the role of people is very important,

requiring each person to make reasonable financial management decisions. (Dang Thuy Linh, et al, 2021)

Personal financial management skills

Personal financial management skills are the application of knowledge to plan for yourself a reasonable spending plan, helping you not only form good habits, and avoid falling into debt but also save some money for investment and set aside a budget for emergencies. (Bui Thi Ngoc Anh, et al, 2020)

2.2. Research overview

Attitudes towards personal financial management skills. Research by Bui Thi Ngoc Anh, et al (2020) shows that attitude towards personal financial management skills is one of three factors affecting the personal financial management skills of business management students at the University of Engineering and Technology, with an impact level of 0.216. Research by Tran Thi Mai Ly, et al (2023) shows that financial attitude is one of three factors that positively influence students' financial management skills. The study also gives implications for financial attitudes, each student should be proactive in learning and understanding economic knowledge to improve and enhance personal financial management skills. Furthermore, students should create their budget and keep track to improve it, which can start by recording all their income and expenses for a month. Then, consider which expenses can be cut, and set specific and clear financial goals to have a reasonable spending plan.

The influence of family environment. Besides factors related to personal characteristics, researchers pointed out that factors related to family circumstances such as parent's education level, parents' occupation, and family economic situation... also have an impact on students' level of financial literacy. (Mohamad, 2010). Murphy (2005) found that students from well-educated families are more financially literate and that regular financial education with parents strengthens students' financial awareness. Lusardi, et al (2010) suggest that a mother's education does have a big impact on a person's financial awareness, especially if the mother has a college degree. Thus, parents' education level has a positive impact on students' financial literacy.

The influence of living and learning environment. The academic ability has been used to predict students' financial literacy and financial well-being in several previous studies (Chen & Volpe (1998), Sabri, et al (2010), Shim, et al (2010)). Jariah, et al (2004) have shown a strong relationship between academic achievement and financial literacy, that students with higher GPA (Grade Point Average) have better financial literacy. Research also shows that students with high GPA tend to learn more financial knowledge from their friends than students with low GPA. In addition, the number of years of study at a university affects students' financial awareness,

specifically, graduates are more knowledgeable than undergraduates, and third- and fourth-year students have better financial awareness than lower-year students.

Awareness of personal financial management. In Vietnam, a study conducted by the World Bank (WB) measured the financial literacy of university students in Hanoi on three aspects: financial knowledge, financial skills, and financial behavior, in which the financial attitude that affects decision-making was included in the financial behavior part. This study shows that the level of personal financial knowledge of students in Hanoi is at an average-poor level. This result is consistent with the results of a survey of students at the University of Southern Mississippi in Floyd’s (2015) study or Nidar & Sandi’s (2012) study at Padjadjaran University of Indonesia.

2.3. Proposed research model, hypothesis, and scale

Based on the theory and research overview, the research team proposes a tentative research model as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Proposed research model

Source: Research team proposal

Research hypothesis

H1. Attitudes towards personal financial management skills are positively related to personal financial management skills among young Vietnamese people

Table 1. Observed variables of factor “Attitude towards personal financial management skills”

Factor	Code	Observed variables	Source
Attitudes toward	ATPM1	I always feel confident and secure when spending wisely.	Bui Thi Ngoc Anh & et al (2020)

personal financial management skills	ATPM2	I always think about how to manage personal finances effectively.
	ATPM3	I always think about planning my daily expenses.
	ATPM4	I am very concerned about my current financial situation.

Source: Reference and synthesis of the research team

H2. The influence of the family environment is positively related to the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people.

Table 2. Observed variables of factor “Influence of family environment”

Factor	Code	Observed variables	Source
The influence of the family environment	IFE1	My family situation affects my financial management.	Bui Thi Ngoc Anh & et al (2020); Kayla Allen (2009)
	IFE2	I am always concerned about my monthly finances by my relatives.	
	IFE3	I am not financially dependent on my family.	
	IFE4	When you have financial problems, relatives will help but not all the time.	
	IFE5	I was taught some basic financial management skills by my family.	

Source: Reference and synthesis of the research team

H3. The influence of living and learning environment is positively related to the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people.

Table 3. Observed variables of factor “Influence of living and learning environment”

Factor	Code	Observed variables	Source
The influence of living and learning environment	ILLE1	The lifestyle of my friends has a big influence on my financial management skills.	Bui Thi Ngoc Anh & et al (2020); Leskinen & Raijas (2006)
	ILLE2	My living environment (housing, friends, entertainment...) is suitable for my financial situation.	

	ILLE3	The courses in the curriculum have honed my financial management skills.	
	ILLE4	My teachers have influenced my financial management skills.	

Source: Reference and synthesis of the research team

H4. Awareness of personal financial management is positively related to the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people.

Table 4. Observed variables of factor “Awareness of personal financial management”

Factor	Code	Observed variables	Source
Awareness of personal financial management	APFM1	Have basic knowledge of personal financial management.	Bui Thi Ngoc Anh & et al (2020); Leila Falahati, Laily Paim, Maimunah Ismail, Sharifah Azizah Haron & Jariah Masud (2011)
	APFM2	Know how to apply learned knowledge into practice.	
	APFM3	Always know how to spend wisely (control your spending)	
	APFM4	I always have a plan for effective financial management.	
	APFM5	Divide money into small amounts according to the ratio (fixed amount, additional amount, incidental amount, etc.)	
	APFM6	I always record my expenses or use personal finance management apps to control my spending.	

Source: Reference and synthesis of the research team

For “Personal financial management skills” according to Xiao, et al (2006) published an FMBS scale, identifying important aspects of personal financial management, including 4 aspects: Spending management, credit management, savings management, investment management, and insurance management. Inheriting the scale of Xiao, et al (2006), the observed variables of the factor “Personal financial management skills” are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Observed variables of factor “Personal financial management skills”

Factor	Code	Observed variables	Source
Personal financial management skills	PFMS1	I have the skills to manage my expenses in my financial capacity.	Xiao & et al (2006), Le Thi Hong Hanh & et al (2023)
	PFMS2	I have the skills to manage income and expenses.	
	PFMS3	I have practiced the skill of managing my expenses economically.	
	PFMS4	I am confident in my investment management and insurance management skills.	

Source: Reference and synthesis of the research team

3. Research Methodology

3.1. The method of data collection

Based on the theory and overview of research on factors affecting the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people, the factors included in the research model include Attitudes towards personal financial management skills (ATPM); The influence of the family environment (IFE); The influence of living and learning environment (ILLE); Awareness of personal financial management (APFM) dependent variable “Personal financial management skills” (PFMS).

The survey was constructed with a 5-point Likert scale, with:

1. *Completely disagree*
2. *Disagree*
3. *Neutral*
4. *Agree*
5. *Completely agree*

Quantitative research methods were conducted to collect opinions from young people in Vietnam (people under 30 years old). After developing the survey, the research team conducted a random pilot survey on 10 young people. The preliminary survey results showed that opinions agreed with the factors included in the model.

Due to time and resource constraints for the survey, the author used a convenience sampling method, the minimum sample size required was calculated according to Hair et al. (2016) who proposed the 10 times rule to determine the minimum sample in PLS. This rule is as follows:

- *Method 1. The minimum sample will be 10 times the number of observed variables of a causal scale (variable) construct with the most observed variables.*

- *Method 2. The minimum sample will be 10 times the number of impact paths directed at a scale structure with the most paths directed at it.*

With the number of factors and observed variables as in the research paper, according to the first method, the minimum sample will be $6 \times 10 = 60$, which is the minimum sample; According to the second method, the minimum sample will be $4 \times 10 = 40$ minimum samples. The subjects surveyed are young people in Vietnam. From the viewpoint that the more observation samples collected, the more stable the impact level is ensured. Based on the ability to collect samples, the research team decided that the number of ballots to be issued is $n > 150$. The form has been sent to the survey subjects by [the link: \(https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf86lR2ChzzSIHsFG6d12E0UD4Fs_DEP1EISGwRMncJhKiRPg/viewform\)](https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf86lR2ChzzSIHsFG6d12E0UD4Fs_DEP1EISGwRMncJhKiRPg/viewform) combined with direct voting. The number of ballots collected was 161, of which 152 were valid ballots from young people in Vietnam (guaranteed to be greater than 60 ballots) and were included in the analysis of influencing factors.

3.2. Data processing method

SMARTPLS software is used to test hypotheses and evaluate the impact level of factors.

Step 1: Evaluate the measurement model

The measurement model is evaluated by considering the contribution of observed variables (outer loadings), the reliability of the scale (Cronbach's Alpha), convergence (Convergence), and discriminant validity (Discriminant Validity).

Step 2: Evaluate the structural model

When the measurement model meets the requirements, proceed to evaluate the structural model through the impact relationship, path coefficient, overall determination coefficient R square, and effect size coefficient f square.

4. Research Results

4.1. Description of survey participants

The survey results received 161 responses, of which 152 valid responses from young people in Vietnam were included in the analysis of influencing factors. Details on gender, occupation, age, living area, and monthly income of the survey subjects are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Descriptive statistics of survey participants

Income	Number of people	Proportion (%)	Ages	Number of people	Proportion (%)
< 10 million VND	78	51.32	Under 18 years old	62	40.79
10-< 20 million VND	40	26.32	From 18 up to 22 years old	60	39.47
20-<50 million VND	25	16.45	From 22 up to 30 years old	30	19.74
Upper 50 million VND	9	5.92	Total	152	100.00
Total	152	100			
Profession	Number of people	Proportion (%)	Gender	Number of people	Proportion (%)
Students	100	65.79	Male	70	46.05
Employed	46	30.26	Female	80	52.63
Other	6	3.95	Not want to be specific	2	1.32
Total	152	100.00		152	100

Source: Survey results

Profession: The survey participants were mainly students with 100 people (65.79%), those who were working 46 people (30.26%), and other subjects such as those who were no longer studying and were looking for a job were 6 people (3.95%).

Ages: The age of the survey participants is mainly from 18-22 years old: 62 people under 18 years old (40.79%), 60 people from 18 to under 22 years old (39.47%), 30 people from 22 to under 30 years old (19.74%).

Income: The income of the survey participants is mainly under 10 million VND/month (78 people, accounting for 51.32%), from 10 to under 20 million VND 40 people, accounting for 26.32%, from 20 to under 50 million VND is 9 people, accounting for 5.92%.

Gender: The gender of the survey participants was 80 female (52.63%), 70 male (46.05%), and 2 people who did not want to specify (1.32%).

4.2. Inspection results

4.2.1. Results of assessing the quality of observed variables in the measurement model

4.2.1.1. Quality control of observed variables

The quality of observed variables is assessed through the outer loadings. The quality of observed variables affecting the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people is shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Outer loadings of factors affecting personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people

	PFMS	IFE	ILLE	APFM	ATPM
PFMS1	0.765				
PFMS2	0.902				
PFMS3	0.891				
PFMS4	0.891				
MTDG1		0.802			
IFE2		0.749			
IFE3		0.769			
IFE4		0.785			
IFE5		0.732			
ILLE1			0.821		
ILLE2			0.876		
ILLE3			0.844		
APFM1				0.834	
APFM2				0.818	
APFM3				0.817	
APFM4				0.733	
APFM5				0.797	
APFM6				0.809	
ATPM2					0.875
ATPM3					0.886
ATPM4					0.762
ATPM1					0.810

Source: Test results of the research team

The results from Table 7 show that the outer loadings of all the total correlation coefficients of the variables affecting the personal financial management skills of Vietnamese youth are all > 0.7 (Hair & et al, 2016), showing that the observed variables are significant.

4.2.1.2. Testing the reliability of the scale

Assessing the reliability of the scale of factors affecting personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people on SMARTPLS through two main indexes: Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR).

Table 8. Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability of Factors Affecting Personal Financial Management Skills of Vietnamese Youth

	Cronbach’s Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
PFMS	0.885	0.885	0.921	0.746
IFE	0.831	0.845	0.878	0.589
ILLE	0.803	0.807	0.884	0.718

APFM	0.889	0.891	0.915	0.643
ATPM	0.854	0.861	0.902	0.697

Source: Test results of the research team

According to Table 8, after analyzing the reliability test using Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient of the factor, the result is: Personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people (PFMS) reached 0.885; The influence of family environment (IFE) reached 0.831; The influence of living and learning environment (ILLE) reached 0.803; Awareness of personal financial management (APFM) reached 0.889; Attitude towards personal financial management skills (ATPM) reached 0.854. Thus, all scales satisfy the condition > 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012) and do not violate any rule of eliminating variables, so no variables are eliminated and can be accepted in terms of reliability.

Composite Reliability (CR) of all observed variables is also > 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). Therefore, the scale is reliable, has analytical significance, and is used in the next factor analysis.

4.2.1.3. Convergence

According to the data analysis results in Table 8, the average variance extracted (AVE) of the factor: Personal financial management skills (PFMS) reached 0.746; the Influence of family environment (IFE) reached 0.589; Influence of living and learning environment (ILLE) reached 0.718; Awareness of personal financial management (APFM) reached 0.643; Attitude towards personal financial management skills (ATPM) reached 0.697.

Thus, the average variance extracted (AVE) index of all variables is > 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010), which shows that the model satisfies the convergence conditions.

4.2.1.4. Discriminant Validity

The results in Table 9 on the Fornell-Larcker index of the research model on factors affecting the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people show that the factors of personal Financial Management Skills (PFMS); Influence of Family Environment (IFE); Influence of living and learning environment (ILLE); Awareness of personal financial management (APFM); Attitudes toward personal financial management (ATPM) skills are all distinctive because all the square root AVE values on the diagonal are higher than their off-diagonal values. Therefore, in terms of discriminant validity, the two criteria including cross-loading coefficient and Fornell and Larcker criteria have satisfied the condition.

Table 9. Fornell-Larcker index of the research model of factors affecting personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people

	PFMS	IFE	ILLE	APFM	ATPM
PFMS	0.864				

IFE	0.579	0.768			
ILLE	0.707	0.570	0.847		
APFM	0.724	0.565	0.783	0.802	
ATPM	0.643	0.483	0.775	0.774	0.835

Source: Test results of the research team

4.2.1.5. f^2 function value

The f^2 function value represents the influence level of the structure (factor) when removed from the model. The f^2 values correspond to 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, which correspond to small, medium, and large effect sizes (Cohen, 1988) of the exogenous variable. If the effect size < 0.02 , then there is no effect.

Table 10. Summary table of f^2 values

	PFMS	IFE	ILLE	APFM	ATPM
PFMS					
IFE	0.061				
ILLE	0.053				
APFM	0.093				
ATPM	0.004				

Source: Test results of the research team

In this model, in Table 10 we see that there are links between IFE (0.061); ILLE (0.053); and APFM (0.093) “have” an impact on personal financial management skills, with $f^2 > 0,02$ considered to have a small impact. ATPM factor (0.004) with $f^2 < 0.02$ is considered to not influence personal financial management skills.

4.2.2. Impact assessment results using structural model

4.2.2.1. Assessing impact relationships

The relationship and level of influence of factors affecting personal financial management skills are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Factors affecting personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people

Source: SMARTPLS test results of the research team

The results of Bootstrap analysis to evaluate the impact relationships are shown in Table 6. Accordingly, the factors “*The influence of the family environment (IFE)*”, “*The influence of living and learning environment (ILLE)*”, and “*Awareness of financial management (APFM)*” have P Values <0.05, This reflects that these factors are statistically significant enough to demonstrate a positive relationship with personal financial management skills. Factor “*Attitude towards personal financial management skills (ATPM)*” has P Values > 0.05, This reflects that this factor is not statistically significant enough to demonstrate a positive relationship with personal financial management skills.

Table 11. Structural model path coefficients (Path Coefficient)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
IFE => PFMS	0.195	0.198	0.094	2.069	0.039
ILLE => PFMS	0.266	0.259	0.099	2.681	0.008
APFM => PFMS	0.350	0.358	0.110	3.194	0.001
ATPM => PFMS	0.072	0.071	0.104	0.688	0.492

Source: SMARTPLS test results of the research team

The test results in Table 11 show that with 95% confidence, “*Awareness of personal financial management*” (APFM) has the strongest influence on “*Personal financial management skills*” with an influence of 0.350; followed by the factor “*The influence of living and learning environment*” (ILLE) with an influence of 0.266, the factor “*The influence of family environment*” (IFE) has an impact level of 0.195 (P values < 0.05). (Accept hypotheses H2, H3, H4)

Factor “*Attitudes towards personal financial management skills*” (ATPM) is not statistically significant enough to conclude about the effect of this variable on “*Personal financial management skills*” (P value > 0.05). (Hypothesis H1 is not accepted)

4.2.2.2. Evaluate the overall determined coefficient R² (R square)

The results of the PLS Algorithm analysis give the value R², reflecting the extent to which the independent variable explains the dependent variable. R² coefficient measure of the overall coefficient of determination (R-square value), which is an index to measure the goodness of fit of the data to the model (the explanatory power of the model). Hair et al. (2010) suggested R-square values at 0.75, 0.50 or 0.25.

Table 12. Coefficient of the level of explanation of the independent variable for the dependent variable (R Square)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
PFMS	0.600	0.590

Source: Test results of the research team

The results from Table 12 show that R² of 0.600 and adjusted R² of 0.590 is suitable in this case study, so the independent variables in the model explain 60% of the variation in the dependent variable “*Personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people*”.

4.2.2.3. Assessing Standardized Root Mean Square Residual Index (SRMR)

Standardized Root Mean Square Residual Index (SRMR): This index indicates the suitability of the research model. According to Hu & Bentler (1999), normally a suitable model will have an SRMR value of less than 0.08 or 0.1.

Table 13. Reliability Index: Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.086	0.086

Source: Test results of the research team

Through the research results, SRMR in Table 13 of the research model is 0.086 < 0.1. Therefore, this model is suitable for data analysis.

The research results show that with 95% confidence, of the four factors considered affecting “*Personal financial management skills of Vietnamese youth*”,

There are 3 factors (statistically significant) showing a positive relationship with personal financial management skills. “*Awareness of personal financial management*” (APFM) has the strongest impact on the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people with an influence level of 0.350, showing that when awareness of personal financial management increases by 1 unit, personal financial management skills increase by 0.350 units; next is the factor “*The influence of living and learning environment*” (ILLE) With an influence level of 0.266, it shows that when the influence factor of living and learning environment increases by 1 unit, the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people increase by 0.266 units and finally, factor “*The influence of family environment*” (IFE) with the effect size of 0.195 shows that when the influence of family environment increases by 1 unit, the personal financial management skills of young Vietnamese people increase by 0.195 units.

5. Some Solutions to Improve the Personal Financial Management Skills of Young Vietnamese People

The research results have shown that 3 factors have a positive impact on the personal financial management skills of Vietnamese youth, including Awareness of personal financial management; Influence of living and learning environment; and Influence of family environment. Therefore, the research team proposes solutions to improve personal financial management skills in 3 aspects: From the young people’s side, from the School (society) side, and the family side as follows:

About solutions from young people

First, Young people need to identify specific, clear financial goals for each stage, including identifying specific personal expenses or short-term, medium-term, and long-term investments. Accordingly, analyze current income and expenses to assess the financial situation of individuals to set up a reasonable spending budget, suitable for income and financial goals, thereby being able to easily monitor and adjust the budget periodically to ensure efficiency.

Second, one of the reasons why young people find it difficult to manage their finances is that they do not know how to allocate their income to their goals. Therefore, one of the ways to improve is to increase income by proactively seeking opportunities for career advancement, developing skills and knowledge to increase self-worth, and proactively participating in side business activities to increase income...

Third, one of the factors to be able to manage personal finances most effectively is saving. Young people need to establish a saving habit as soon as they have income, automate saving by using financial planning tools to estimate expenses, track income, and expenses, and manage...

Fourth, Young people need to change their spending habits. Instead of shopping emotionally or following trends, they need to spend reasonably, make a list before going shopping, and only spend on necessary goods. The current reality is that young people spend a lot on eating out and buying goods and products that do not serve essential needs but only follow trends. Therefore, young people should cook for themselves instead of eating out, buy essential goods instead of following trends...

On the School (society) side

First, schools need to raise awareness of the importance of financial education, by organizing seminars and forums to promote the importance of financial education to staff, teachers, parents, and students, integrating financial education into extracurricular activities such as extracurricular activities, collective activities, and using the school's communication channels to promote financial education.

Second, schools need to include financial education in their curriculum, integrating knowledge about personal financial management skills into subjects, especially Math, Civic Education, etc. Encourage extracurricular activities on financial education, and establish clubs so that students can exchange and learn experiences on personal financial management.

Third, schools need to create a learning environment that encourages saving and spending wisely. Avoid waste and spending indiscriminately and unreasonably. Encourage students to participate in community service activities to help practice thrift, respect for money, and a sense of sharing with the community.

On the family side

First, families need to create a learning environment that encourages children to be financially independent. For example, families can let young people freely decide how to spend a portion of their pocket money, or for students, they can let young people manage their expenses in renting a house, eating, and living... and only intervene when they notice waste in spending.

Second, families need to motivate and be role models for young people in personal financial management skills. Parents should plan their family's spending and stick to it, save and invest wisely, and avoid waste, excessive debt, investing or spending on improper purposes...

Third, Families should actively discuss and be open with young people about financial issues, and can share with their children about income, how to allocate spending, and plan the family's finances. Explain to young people the reasons and consequences of all family financial decisions and encourage them to proactively ask questions, and share their thoughts on financial issues, and difficulties in financial management so that the family can intervene and support them promptly.

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